

Some Investigations of Molecular Interactions

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THIS lecture is being prepared very hurriedly, so it will be brief and unscholarly; but this same pressure of time may have the advantage of forcing selection and thus of improving the perspective in which the work is seen.

The author has always been interested in valence and bonding, but mostly in definite bonds—the kind that confer enough stability on a substance for it to be isolated and put in a bottle. There have long been known, however, bonds which are weaker and yet are chemically significant. Of these one of the most familiar types is the hydrogen bond. About ten years ago the author began to take more interest in these weaker kinds of bonding, and this lecture describes some of the consequences.

On reflection, it soon becomes apparent that we have to consider and to decide what it is we are looking for. All substances exist in condensed phases; so all molecules attract. The physical chemist tends to limit his interest to those attractions which can be expressed by general potential functions. For these potential functions to be deemed satisfactory, they should explain quantitatively such equilibrium properties as crystal structure, density virial coefficients, and Joule-Thomson coefficients, and also transport properties such as thermal conductivity and viscosity. Moreover, if a potential function is to be deemed general it should have commutative properties in mixtures, e.g. if the potential functions between A and B, and between B and C are known, then that between C and A should be predictable.

Anything like an exact solution of these problems, even for the simplest molecules—those of the inert gases—proves very difficult. If, therefore, one is interested in the interactions between more complicated molecules, especially those significant in biology, the task of finding a rigorous treatment is immensely more difficult. The chemist has, however, always known the virtues of compromise; so he looks to see what degree of rigour can usefully be aimed for.

Adverting to the question of what it is that the author was looking for, the answer is something in between those interactions which ideally are describable by general potential functions, which we may call physical interactions, and those which produce definite new compounds, which we may call chemical. This area in between is large and it is, so to speak, grey. “Chemical” implies a fair degree of specificity; but it may be difficult to decide whether apparent anomalies of interaction are really specific or whether they are merely a measure of the badness of our physics. One has, therefore, to be careful in drawing conclusions and one must, following traditional chemical methodology, look for patterns of behaviour.

The next question is what in general terms can the chemist do? One measure of interaction which he commonly uses is the equilibrium constant, or formation constant, in an interaction such as

expressed as

$$K_f = [AB]/[A][B] \quad (2)$$

From studies on e.g. electrolytes we know that this treatment is inappropriate unless the species A, B, and AB are independent and distinct, that is unless they move independently and have distinct vibrations and rotations. This requires that the forces between A and B must be of relatively short range and saturable so that there are only collisional forces between AB and either A or B, and that AB must have a sufficient lifetime for the new vibrations and rotations to be established and become manifest. The effects of long range interactions, for example between oppositely charged pairs of ions, or of interactions in very brief encounters, cannot be properly treated in this way. Other forms of assessment must be sought.

Detection of interaction depends upon being able to measure some property which in the complex

AB is different from what it is for A or B or for the sum of these two. Vibration frequencies have been much used in examining hydrogen-bonding, and so have other spectroscopic properties like chemical shifts. Electronic spectroscopy has been very widely used ; but this is a function both of the ground and of the excited electronic states, so it does not reveal quite what is happening in either one of these states alone.

Dielectric properties should be useful for this task. Unless the interaction takes place symmetrically between two identical molecules, there is an asymmetric perturbation of the electron distribution within the molecules which gives rise to a new electric dipole moment of the complex or changes the value which might be predicted by a vector summation of the moments of the interacting species if the stereochemistry of the complex is known. This process is one of mutual induction, and in general it is to be deemed chemical rather than physical because it cannot usually be adequately described in terms of a permanent physical moment in one molecule inducing a moment in another by virtue of the linear polarization of the latter.

Another process, in principle independent, is the change of average mutual orientation of permanent dipoles in the two interacting molecular species. This may happen between two identical molecules with permanent dipoles and is most simply illustrated by this system. In the limit, when complex formation causes rigid arrangement, two such molecules are likely to form either a non-polar complex with two antiparallel moments (a)

Fig. 1. The polar extremes for dimerization of a polar substance.

or a polar one with two parallel moments (b). Because there is only half the number of molecules after complex formation has occurred, but because the orientation polarization is $\propto \mu^2$, each of the original molecules has an *effective* dipole moment of $\sqrt{2}\mu$, the complex itself having a *resultant* moment 2μ .

By measuring the polarization of the substance, not only may complex formation be detected from

non-additivity but information about the stereochemistry of the complex and possibly about induced moment changes due to interaction may be obtained.

The effects of change of average mutual orientation for a single substance in the vapour phase have been elegantly formalized by A. D. Buckingham and J. Pople¹ who have shown that it is convenient to express the total electric polarization as a virial expansion

$$\tau^P = \left(\frac{\epsilon-1}{\epsilon+2} \right) V_m = \mathcal{A} + \frac{\mathcal{B}}{V_m} + \dots \quad (3)$$

ϵ being the dielectric constant of the gas and V_m the molar volume. \mathcal{A} , \mathcal{B} etc. are called the dielectric virial coefficients. \mathcal{B} shows the effect of pair interactions.

If, more generally, we are dealing with a mixture of two components (substances 1 and 2), then it can be shown that it is possible to separate out \mathcal{B}_{12} if the values of \mathcal{B}_{11} and \mathcal{B}_{22} are known, as it is also for the density virial coefficient B_{12} ; and then

$$-\frac{\mathcal{B}_{12}}{B_{12}} = \frac{4\pi\mathcal{N}}{9kT} \{ \langle \mu_{12}^2 \rangle - (\mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2) \}$$

So, if $\langle \mu_{12}^2 \rangle$ is greater than the average for no interaction, viz. $\mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2$, \mathcal{B}_{12} is positive, because B_{12} must be negative when there is association—in fact

$$B_{12} = -K_1/2 \quad (5)$$

conversely if $\langle \mu_{12}^2 \rangle < (\mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2)$, \mathcal{B}_{12} must be negative. By studying T^P as a function of pressure, it is therefore possible to decide what the stereochemistry of the complexing is. Furthermore, if \mathcal{B}_{12} is positive, showing parallel alignment of dipoles, and if $\langle \mu_{12}^2 \rangle > (\mu_1 + \mu_2)^2$ there is clear evidence of mutual polarization.

These tests have been applied by several people working with Professor A. D. Buckingham and myself, viz. Dr. R. Raab, Dr. K. P. Lawley, Dr. D. J. Turner and Dr. Barnes with Dr. W. D. Haworth. In the U. S. A. measurements relating to the same general treatment have been made by Professor Robert H. Cole and his pupils, including even some for inert gases. The measurements prove to be extremely difficult technically, and the errors, particularly in the early measurements, are larger than could be wished. Nevertheless, it has been possible to draw some general conclusions.

We might first consider what we should expect to find. The simplest model of interaction between polar molecules is that due to Professor W. H. Stockmayer². This is to represent the polar molecules as spheres with physical electric dipoles at their centres. Because the potential energy of the arrangement (b)

FIG. 2

The dimerization of Stockmayer model dipoles.

is twice that of arrangement (a), both being negative, this model would predict that B should always be positive.

Not surprisingly, this simple model is easily proved inadequate. A very large negative B value (ca -10^6 cm⁶ mol⁻²) was found for methyl cyanide by Buckingham and Raab³ and a smaller but still definitely negative value for methyl chloride was found independently by Sutter and Cole⁴ and by Barnes^{5a}.

Possible reasons are that these molecules are cigar-shaped, so the potential energy of arrangement (a) is lower than that of (b), or that the dipoles are

TABLE 1. OBSERVED VALUES OF B

molecule	T/°C	this work		previous work	
		T/°C	B /cm ⁶ mol ⁻²	T/°C	B /cm ⁶ mol ⁻²
fluoroform	30.0		1330 ± 100	19.4	3100 ± 2400
			1300 ± 160		
	50.0		1120 ± 200	50.0	1125 ± 52
			1110 ± 160		
chlorodifluoromethane	70.0		980 ± 200		
				80.5	1200 ± 1600
				96.3	903 ± 20
dimethyl ether	30.0		2600 ± 200		
			2300 ± 200		
	70.0		1800 ± 200		
methyl chloride				21.5	4000 ± 1000
				40.3	2600 ± 1000
				61.5	2400 ± 1000
				5.0	-8500 ± 1800
1,1 difluoroethylene				25.0	-10200 ± 1400
	30.0		-6200 ± 1200		
			-7100 ± 1400		
				45.0	-8500 ± 1500
	50.0		-3550 ± 600	50.0	-4470 ± 200
			-3800 ± 800		
chlorotrifluoromethane					
				96.3	-2517 ± 50
				131.6	-1696 ± 60
	30.0		-715 ± 160		
dichlorodifluoromethane					
	50.0		-730 ± 100		
chlorotrifluoromethane					
	50.0		-440 ± 100		
dichlorodifluoromethane					
	50.0		-480 ± 100		
dichlorodifluoromethane					
	50.0		-420 ± 80		
dichlorodifluoromethane					
	50.0		-240 ± 100		
dichlorodifluoromethane					
	50.0		30 ± 200	50.0	60 ± 5
dichlorodifluoromethane					
	50.0		25 ± 200		
dichlorodifluoromethane					
	50.0		400 ± 600*		
dichlorodifluoromethane					
	50.0		270 ± 200		
dichlorodifluoromethane					
	50.0		200 ± 140		
dichlorodifluoromethane					
	50.0		-400 ± 1000*		

*obtained from high-pressure measurements of ϵ and p .

From A. N. M. BARNES and L. E. SUTTON, Trans. Faraday Soc. 1971, 67, 2919.

off-centre which also makes this potential energy relationship possible, as K. P. Lawley and E. B. Smith⁶ showed :

FIG. 3

The dimerization of (a) rod-shaped dipoles
(b) spherical, off-centre dipoles.

Either variation of the model requires the introduction of a new parameter ; and this makes prediction more difficult. Despite the persistence and ingenuity of Dr. Barnes, it proved difficult to provide satisfactory and consistent explanations of the behaviour of single substances. For some binary mixtures it proved impossible to explain the behaviour in terms of a single set of parameters for each substance.

Here then was an example of the uncertainty to which I referred earlier. Was this breakdown due to the inadequacy of the physical model or to specific, chemical types of interaction ?

It was very noticeable that some mixtures gave values of \mathcal{B}_{12} which were much larger than those guessed by a simple mixture rule, and in these it was likely that there was weak hydrogen-bonding, e.g. in dimethylether with fluoroform or chlorodifluoromethane or hydrogen chloride, or that there was weak electron donor-acceptor interaction, e.g. in dimethylether and sulphur dioxide.

For the dimethylether/fluoroform system there is a measured value of B_{12} , so the value of $\langle \mu_{12}^2 \rangle^{\frac{1}{2}}$ can be evaluated from equation (4)^{5b}. It is 2.50D, which is less than the value for complete alignment (2.95D) but larger than the value for random orientation, viz. $(\mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ which is 2.09D. B_{12} gives (equation 5) a small value of K_t , only 1.35l mol., yet this corresponds to an interaction which is strong enough in the actual pairs to have a profound effect upon the rotational behaviour of the molecules form-

TABLE 2. EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF \mathcal{B}_{12}

mixture	T/°C	$\mathcal{B}_{12}/\text{cm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2}$	$\frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{B}_{11} + \mathcal{B}_{22})$
Me ₂ O + CHF ₃	*19	27 000 ± 2000	1950 ± 1000
	50	16 800 ± 1500	1350 ± 150
	70	11 850 ± 800	1250 ± 150
Me ₂ O + CHF ₂ Cl	30	24 000 ± 2000	2700 ± 300
	50	18 000 ± 1200	1950 ± 150
	70	12 500 ± 700	1750 ± 200
Me ₂ O + SO ₂	*18.5	46 000 ± 3000	2250 (19.5°C)
	*40	27 000 ± 1000	—
Me ₂ O + HCl	*19.5	450 000 ± 5000	3400
Me ₂ O + CH ₂ CF ₂	70	1 400 ± 700	700 ± 200
Me ₂ O + CH ₃ Cl	50	1 100 ± 1000	
		-750 ± 1000	-1000 ± 300
	70	900 ± 800	
		1 000 ± 500	-500 ± 250
CHF ₃ + CHF ₂ Cl	50	950 ± 400	1700 ± 100
	70	150 ± 600	1400 ± 200
CHF ₃ + CH ₂ Cl	70	-800 ± 600	-850 ± 200
CHF ₃ + CH ₂ CF ₂	50	950 ± 200	350 ± 100

*ref. (8)

From A. N. M. BARNES and L. E. SUTTON, Trans. Faraday Soc. 1971, 67, 2927.

some day we may be able to make these counterpart observations.

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